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Innovation in Continuing Engineering Education with focus on gender and non-traditional students' pathways

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ABSTRACT

The challenges of the 21st century call for supporting Continuing Engineering Education, a topic that is of increasing importance to universities worldwide. Furthermore, attracting new talents (women among others) into Engineering Education, is a key-element in contemporary higher education. Although the offer of studying programs alongside work has grown in recent years, there is still a need for research in context of accompanied studies and a lack of theory-based development in didactic concepts for learning professionals. This paper contributes to this research discourse and aims to generate new insights in a threefold way: (1) by specifying challenges and innovative approaches for accompanied studying programs in Business Engineering; (2) by explaining the theoretical framework for the methodical arrangement of exemplary engineering courses for non-traditional students; and (3) by describing first experiences with the concept during the development and implementation in selected engineering course. This paper also provides a new perspective on how to meet gender aspects. In this context, the influences of interdisciplinary orientation and student- centered course design were analyzed by using semi-structured interviews with female students.

Conference Key Areas: Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning, Engineering Education Research, Gender and Diversity

Keywords: Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning, University-Business cooperation, Curriculum Development, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Gender and Diversity

INTRODUCTION

Recent socio- political and economic developments call for supporting Continuing Engineering Education, [1, 2]. Furthermore, attracting new talents into Engineering Education is a key-element in contemporary higher education. One approach to react to the strong demand is the broadening of the target group with an increased focus on non-traditional students, as in [3]. Although the offer of studying programs alongside work has grown in recent years, there is still a lack of theory-based development in

targeted didactic concepts and associated empirical findings [4]. There is still a need for research in context of accompanied studies and student-centered contact with the specific target groups of learning professionals, e.g. [5, 6]. This paper contributes to this research discourse. In section 1, the term “non-traditional student” is specified and a professional master’s degree program for this specific target group is presented. Section 2 deals particularly with the theory-based course design for this specific type of students and illustrates the Model of Educational Reconstruction as an applicable framework for this methodical educational arrangement. Building on this, section 3 illustrates the implementation of the concept in selected engineering courses and describes first experiences with the concept. Section 4 covers gender aspects and debates, which framework conditions of the concept are beneficial to the motivation and participation of female students. Additionally, it addresses the opportunities that arise for occupational study programs. This approach generates empirically grounded knowledge on the theory-based course design for learning professionals and contributes to the translation of engineering education research to practice. Universities will have to face these challenges, in living up to the requirements of change processes in a sustainable manner.

1 CHALLENGES FOR CONTINUING ENGINEERING EDUCATION

1.1 Occupational study programs in Germany

Due to the demographic transformation into ageing societies and to the rapid pace of technological change, the European University Association recommended in their 2008 preamble [1] to open to continuous education. Since then, German universities have followed this central educational objective by opening universities to lifelong learning more intensively and by supporting flexible learning pathways, as in [2]. The group of lifelong learners is very heterogeneously, a differentiation is made in [7]. This paper focuses on the employed learners, those working full or part time during their studies. They show “...circumstantial diversity with age differences, disabilities, employment status, caring responsibilities or different financial backgrounds” [8]. Additionally, we find a diversity regarding their motivation, interest, and learning styles, e.g. in [7, 8]. In Germany, there are more than 130 engineering occupational master programs. Of these offered study programs, 13 are master programs in business engineering, which build the focus of this paper.

1.2 Professional master’s degree program in Business engineering: Research-to-practice contribution with focus on non-traditional students

To attract new target groups (women among others) as well as prospective students from working life, an innovative Professional Master’s degree in Business Engineering was conceived, that focuses on the intersection of management and technology. As a specific feature, the engineering master’s program is designed for *non-traditional students*, experienced professionals who do not originate from a technical field and who are repeatedly confronted with technical issues in the occupational context. The business engineering master’s degree is scheduled on the weekend. It is a four term (90 credit points) extra-occupational study program combining engineering content with business specialization¹. This Master of Science program is now in its fourth iteration. The courses are designed with a focus on industrial production, combining the complex links between technology, business, and management. In the first semester scientific and engineering fundamentals are taught. The second and third semester include more detailed engineering courses as well as more complex topics

¹ To which extent these specific features of the study model are appealing especially to women, see within the scope of the qualitative study in Sec. 4.

that deal with the connection between technical and economic content. Throughout the entire study period, complementary courses offered that accompany the study (for example courses in leadership). The master course “Applied Engineering Sciences” presented exemplarily in this paper to explain the theory-based course design is from the field of scientific and engineering fundamentals.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH-BASED COURSE DESIGN OF THE EXEMPLARY ENGINEERING COURSE

2.1 The Framework of Educational Reconstruction with focus on continuing engineering education

The focus on non-traditional students’ pathways brings up the challenge of linking the course design and the individual learning process of the employed learners. This contribution dedicates to the research desiderates, e.g. [4-6], by presenting the Model of Educational Reconstruction. This theoretical framework was chosen because of its consistent student-centered conception. In general, the Model of Educational Reconstruction is a research framework widely used in scientific education, see [9, 10]. There are first results concerning the implementation of this adopted model in engineering, [11]. As a novelty, the model is implemented with a focus on employed learners, who do not originate from a technical field. Fig. 1 shows the generic model adapted for the field of engineering sciences and non-traditional employed learners.

Fig. 1. The Model of Educational Reconstruction with focus on non-traditional employed learners: framework and methods used, based on [9, 11]

Constructivist learning theories, such as [12], build the theory framework, described by the teaching methodology triple [13]. There are three elements that interact- detecting of students’ perspectives, the clarification of experts’ conceptions, and the didactical structuring, [ibid]. The unique characteristic of this triplet is the equivalence of experts’ conceptions and students’ perspectives. To implement the model, all research steps A to E (see fig.1) had to be completed. In order to grasp the variety of aspects in a scientific manner, quantitative and qualitative research methods are used, according to the research steps A to E in fig. 1. Firstly, the students’ conceptions about electro-technical concepts must be collected based on students’ self-report (**step A**). Besides

socio-demographic data, motivation to study, and background on technical subjects, the report contains questions for the employed learners about the current conception of engineering basics. At the same time, the scientific clarification as analysis from the literature is being prepared in **step B**. What do the concepts look like in science? What scientific models exist and where can coherences and limits of the imagination be found? In **step C**, the learners' understanding about the technical theory is reflected and differences between scientific perspectives and the perspectives of the learners are disclosed. Are there existing correspondences to the scientific model? At which point can you build on the learners' conceptions? As result of this correlation, research-based findings exist that prescribe what should be regarded while introducing terms, concepts, and models to the students. Furthermore, with the goal of fostering the students' learning process, the result of the correlation proposes the appropriate interventions that are most likely to be successful. These interventions will be developed in correspondence to the framework of constructivist learning theories and implemented in an engineering teaching practice in **step D**, the result of this design phase is presented within the next section. A final evaluation by students' self-reports on knowledge base within the engineering topics (**step E**) delivers empirical evidence about the effectiveness of the courses. Further feedback from the students has been incorporated into the process of improvement of the course design.

2.2 Research-based Course design

The course design is based on the theoretical frameworks of constructivist learning theories, e.g. [12], and gender theories focusing on STEM education, e.g. [14,15]. Besides these theoretical frameworks, the analysis of the Educational Reconstruction has shown that the methodological-didactic construction of the courses needs to be understood consequentially from the learning process of the individual. The analysis of the students' conception revealed an extremely wide spread in every evaluated category (e.g. age, professional position, motivation). On the one hand, the self-rated technical backgrounds are similarly low. On the other hand, the non-traditional learners have expanded professional and everyday experience. This extended experience is not yet actively retrieved by the student as transfer knowledge, the link to the field of engineering cannot be made yet. Referring to the Model of Educational Reconstruction, these students' conceptions must be incorporated actively in the student-centered course design, to achieve an individual and optimal adoption for the best possible learning outcome and the development of the students' professional competence. The engineering fundamentals should be presented with a focus on taking up the professional context. The mentioned directives are anchored in the didactic concept, presented below:

- *Lectures* as on-site-events with practical examples selected from priority themes (presented by the teacher or the students),
- *Laboratory sequences* integrated into the lectures to anchor the link between theory and practice and to get hands-on experience, and
- *Guided self-study* with reflection and feedback phases (step-by-step conception of exercises fitted for the non-traditional target group, self-control must be possible permanently, online part with the teacher for feedback and reflection).

The theory-based course design guarantees appropriate learning activities for the non-traditional students and supports their learning process.

3 IMPLEMENTATION AND FIRST EXPERIENCES WITH THE CONCEPT

As an example, the implementation of the didactic design into the master course “Applied Engineering Sciences” is presented, currently running in its fourth iteration. The course provides the engineering basis for further specialist modules. Required outcomes are developing technical-methodological skills (e.g. basic techniques and engineering practices in the handling of simple electrical and mechanical problems) and developing practical knowledge (e.g. the analysis of equivalent circuits, the use of appropriate methods and instruments). The **laboratory sequences**, developed and adapted to the core statements of the course, are integrated to overcome the analysed specific deficits in practical preliminary knowledge. Driven by the theoretical framework, the laboratory session is often the starting point of the lessons. This procedure enables to address the unique deficiencies and baseline knowledge of the non-traditional students. Within laboratory group work, a continuous self-control of the students is applied and technical and methodical questions arise. Due to the small number of students, an individual support of the learning process during the experiments is possible, so the students can work out their necessary technical and methodical competencies. The **guided self-study time** was intended to adapt to the strong heterogeneity, to overcome deficits, and to strengthen the individual learning process of the employed students. Exercises concretely oriented toward the contents of the given lectures have been conceived that can be permanently worked on and that provide the opportunity for self-control. Detailed solutions are available for the student to validate their own considerations or to initialize the solving process. Content of the lectures is continually worked on, and a connection to the lectures is made by “do it yourself”. In this way, the self-study time supports flexible learning styles and forms individual ways of learning.

First **positive experiences** with the concept are available. In the survey, every student self-reported a knowledge increase in electrical engineering. A further reference is the fact that every previous student completed the module and the exam successfully. In respect to the didactic course design, the employed students mentioned the practical laboratory part as very helpful. As additional effects, the integration of practical experiments shows an increase in interaction between teacher and students, a transfer of this culture of closer communication and direct feedback into the lectures became possible. Through the interweaving of economic problems and engineering education, a win-win situation for students and teachers is given. Not only is the transfer of new technologies into professional practice supported, but the students’ input from their professional experience provides valuable feedback for the full-time courses.

4 QUALITATIVE STUDY TO EXPLORE GENDER ASPECTS

4.1 Targets and theoretical foundation of the study

Female employees are, as initially illustrated, clearly underrepresented in the STEM² sector and therefore are, alongside non-traditional students, a further and important target group. The aim of this qualitative study via guideline-based interviews is to analyze, if the professional master’s degree program in Business Engineering can be a successful measure to acquire female potential for STEM-studies. Moreover, the framework conditions to successfully address women concerning a further education in engineering will be developed. An important role for the decision to study in the STEM sector play the self-efficacy beliefs, e.g. in [16]. The theoretical construct of self-efficacy was introduced by Bandura [17]. It describes a subjective confidence in one’s own competencies to carry out actions successfully and to be able to meet

² STEM stands for science, technology, engineering and math.

expectations, e.g. in [18]. These statements are especially relevant in respect to the gender aspect, hence the construct of self-efficacy influenced the theoretical foundation of the guideline-based interviews and their evaluation. In addition, references to practical orientation and interdisciplinarity were examined in the interviews. Among others, Thaler and Hofstätter [19] highlight in this context a strong link concerning the decision for an engineering study.

4.2 Methodology and implementation of the analysis

Regarding the continuing engineering education, goals of the qualitative study were on the one hand to collect statements regarding the organization of the study model and to the learners' requirements. On the other hand, the interview study is used to identify the students' backgrounds, and the motivation for the field of engineering. For this purpose, the guideline covers the key issues mentioned above. Beside the socio-demographic data, educational background and the motivation to start studying were collected. The recorded interviews have been completely transcribed, while a memo was created for each interviewee. The assessment of the interviews in transcript was done in accordance with the procedure of qualitative content analysis [20] and under consideration of the in 4.1 explained theory. The interview survey includes seven interviews with first and second year female students of the master degree „Business Engineering“. Hereafter, the female students will be denoted as interview person (IP 1-7). The women are between 22 and 30 years old, after a bachelor's degree in economics the female students have been working in the industrial sector.

4.3 Selected empirical findings and elaboration of the potentials for Continuing Engineering Education

The analysis of the interviews yielded results on several levels. In this paper, the focus lies on the aspects motivation to study, self-efficacy and student-centered course design. Almost all interviewees stated that the **motivation to study a technological discipline** is an insufficient technical know-how and a restricted judgement concerning technical issues and problems. Since they, as a consequence, felt constrained in their professional career an urge to study further in the technical area developed.

“And when discussions regarding specific topics arose, I reached my limit when I realized that my dialogue partner could tell me anything. I was not able to validate anything and only understood some problems after asking again or doing further research. That was when I realized that technology interests me and that I want to dive deeper into this topic.” (IP 4)

Concerning **self-efficacy** and confidence the analysis of the interviews distinctly indicates that a successful first degree and professional experience in the industrial context are to be interpreted as beneficial. IP 5 describes how she gained insight on the structures of an industrial concern through her occupation and detected that she possesses the skill to position herself technologically:

“(...) that is why I gathered all of my courage and said to myself: I have already achieved a lot and have proved myself in my first academic degree, which gave me strength once before. And now I will simply take my chances.” (IP5)

IP 2 shares this experience. She also gained access to technological coherences as well as dismantled barriers through her professional career:

“During my occupational experience, I realized that innovation is very fun-looking into the future and trying to see where the (technological) journey will go. But as innovation is always tangent to technology (...) I realized during my professional career that I am interested in these things as well.” (IP 2)

The selected statements confirm the results of the analysis, which prove an increased self-efficacy concerning the beginning of a technical study through previous occupational and academic achievements. Furthermore, the results show the particular importance of a ***strong connection between theory and practice within the master's degree program as well as the significance of interdisciplinary content and a close connection to the professional profile***. Most of the interviewees stated, that they only after the career entry got a clear understanding of professions and possibilities in the technological segment. As for example IP2, *"It was only during my professional career and with growing experience that I came to realize what engineers do"*. It shows, that often a vague (or unattractive) occupational profile of the engineer exists, which discourages from a technical first degree. Within this context, Ihsen [21] constitutes that universities offer too few initiatives to renew outdated views on technical course of studies. Additional, the interviewees positively rated the interdisciplinary approach in conjunction with technical and economic study content. They especially underline the possibility to enhance an economic first degree with a follow-up degree in the technical area.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER WORK

Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning is an exciting and growing research area within higher engineering education. This paper presents a professional master program "Business Engineering", which innovatively targets students without a previous engineering degree. This specific non-traditional target group as well as female students were directly addressed while developing the program. The paper shows that the Model of Educational Reconstruction is well suited to execute a fitting course design for learning professionals in a theory-based manner. This student-centered framework is particularly valuable for the research discourse in this field. With the implementation of the theory-based course design a contribution to the translation of engineering education research into practice was made. The qualitative study with a focus on gender aspects underlines the positive impacts of a strong conjunction between theory and professional experience and of the interdisciplinary adaption of the master program. The next step is to expand the qualitative study on the full-time Master's to deepen the gender-relevant insights and to explore potentials for the improvement of the master programs. Moreover, the results of the study provide valuable insights for specific student recruitment and counseling.

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